

Source: Khodaei, M. M., [Alizadeh, A.](#), & Haghypour, M. (2019). Preparation and characterization of isatin complexed with Cu supported on 4-(aminomethyl) benzoic acid-functionalized Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles as a novel magnetic catalyst for the Ullmann coupling reaction. *Research on Chemical Intermediates*, 45, 2727–2747. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11164-019-03760-0>. [10.1007/s11164-019-03760-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11164-019-03760-0).

Preparation and characterization of isatin complexed with Cu supported on 4-(aminomethyl) benzoic acid-functionalized Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles as a novel magnetic catalyst for the Ullmann coupling reaction

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Abstract

Isatin complexed with Cu supported on 4-(aminomethyl) benzoic acid-functionalized Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles (Cu-IS-AMBA-MNPs) as a new catalyst was designed, prepared and characterized by appropriate analyses. The heterogeneous reusable catalyst was successfully used for the efficient and widespread syntheses of diarylethers and diarylamines via the Ullmann coupling reaction. This green catalyst was easily removed, reused several times with no significant loss of its activity, and provided a clean synthesis with excellent yield and reduced time.

Keywords: Magnetically recoverable nanocatalyst, Ullman coupling reaction, Nanoparticles, Diaryl ethers, Copper